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INTERFERENCE IN TRANSFER IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Annotation: *Due to globalization and technological development of the world, almost every person is in an atmosphere of multilingualism, when he not only has to deal with different languages besides his native one, but also use different languages depending on the situation of communication. All these contacting languages inevitably influence each other both at the level of individual use and globally, at the level of society.*

Key words: *multilingualism, transfer, transfer problems, negative and positive transfer, second language acquisition, interference.*

All people have interference phenomena (negative influence of the first language on the second) and transfer (positive transfer of skills from one language to another). The article identifies language interference that appears while learning several foreign languages, in addition it explores transfer problems in second language acquisition.

It is not so much about the confusion of languages, i.e. the simultaneous use of lexical units of different languages, namely the unconscious transfer of structural norms and systems of one language to the norms of another, which leads to violations of the norms of the second language and, to one degree or another, imperfect possession. In terms of bilingualism, this phenomenon is expressed in the influence of the prevailing native language on all other languages being studied and is called "interference".

It is necessary to differentiate the phenomena of positive and negative transfer. The influence of the native language (past linguistic experience) on the foreign language being studied can be positive, facilitating the formation of new speech skills, and negative, making it difficult to acquire new knowledge, skills and abilities.

More L.V. Shcherba spoke about the deforming influence of the first language in the study of other languages, although the term "interference" appeared much later. In modern science, the term "interference" means the interaction of language systems in the context of bilingualism or multilingualism. Many scientists are unanimous in their opinion that the action of interference has only a negative result, and this is a process of deviation from the norms of the contacting languages, changes in the structure and elements of languages under the influence of each other.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

The process of mastering a foreign language is necessarily accompanied in the mind of a bilingual by the interaction of two language systems - the native language and the foreign one.

Moreover, this process is considered to be bilateral, since there is an influence of both the native language on the foreign language, and vice versa. For example, given the colossal role of the English language in the modern world, it should be recognized that it also provokes changes in the use of other languages and in some cases becomes a leader language even over the native one, determining its use by a person.

In science, different types of interference are distinguished depending on the level of the language. In this article, we will focus on interference in the most susceptible to change aspects of the language - interference in vocabulary and grammar, which determine the process of speech production and communication in any language.

However, it can be not only unconscious, but also conscious if the teacher involves students in comparing languages. Students with a good level of preparation in the first foreign language, especially those whose skills and abilities in the first language were formed consciously, resort to conscious transfer independently and very actively.

In particular, at the lexical level, the vocabulary of two languages merges into a single lexical fund, concepts and concepts are introduced into one language from another, in other words, this is the interference of the vocabulary of one language system into another. Borrowed vocabulary can at first be equally used together with the old vocabulary, but later either completely replaces the old word, or acquires a highly specialized meaning, provided that both words are preserved in the language.

Also, while maintaining both the old and the new concepts, they can be divided according to style and scope of use, for example, newly arrived words can receive the status of refined, sublime, or, conversely, end up in the list of jargon or elements of vulgar speech.

However, the process of borrowing new words from other languages (now most often from English) occurs uncontrollably, almost chaotically and without human intervention, so now the problem of excessive introduction of English vocabulary into the Uzbek language is becoming more and more acute. In addition, anglicisms come to the Uzbek language along with their grammatical characteristics in terms of gender, number, combination with a verb, and thus affect the use of "neighboring" Uzbek words and the construction of statements.

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KNOWLEDGE